

Urban design ‘without’ and ‘with’ scientific rigour

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The impact of scientific rigour in urban design can be illustrated through the hypothetical example of redesigning part of a neighbourhood, including several urban blocks. Currently, such a project is likely to be undertaken by a team from a private company, typically led by architects. Surprisingly, it is often unnecessary to have an urban design license to be eligible to undertake such a project. These architects will produce several proposals, each including a variety of new plazas, public open spaces, and a mix of residential and commercial complexes. In their proposals, they only need to follow certain zoning or land-use regulations, which are loosely defined by a larger-scale masterplan for that area of the city. All buildings are rendered at their best using fascinating, aesthetically appealing visual techniques, ranging from artistic overall drawing sketches to virtual reality visualisations. However, there is hardly any science-based evidence for these appealing aesthetics. It is unclear how much of these architects' creativity is based on science or simply on their personal feelings, which cannot be assessed by scientific methods. The design process normally involves some degree of stakeholder engagement or, at best, consultation with some residents through various forms of meetings. Their proposals might also consider some broader environmental and economic implications. The absence of a scientific framework for stakeholder involvement, evidence-based knowledge of key design elements, and evaluation methods for design claims before implementation creates uncertainty throughout the process. Ultimately, we may receive a design proposal including a mix of claims and untested statements. Such a proposal may proceed to the implementation phase, and after a few years, we will begin to observe its effects. In most cases, the resulting space might appear aesthetically pleasing but could lack essential elements such as adequate green spaces, accessible pedestrian pathways, and social interaction zones. Even in a few cases where the outcome is effective, there is no scientifically documented procedure on how to replicate such a design process, as none of the steps followed a scientific method.

In contrast, adopting a clinical medicine-style approach to urban design would substantially change both the process and the outcomes. At first, it would ensure that the project is led by certified urban designers who have received urban design training. Then, this approach would begin with a comprehensive review of existing research to identify the best evidence that aligns with the project's goals. Urban design elements and types of interventions would be selected based on systematic reviews and meta-analyses, with decisions well-supported by reliable evidence. Additionally, stakeholder feedback would be systematically gathered through

surveys and community workshops, using science-based frameworks to ensure that the urban design aligns with residents' preferences and needs. The documentation of all details for developing each proposal would be conducted transparently. The selection committee would evaluate the proposals based on measurable evidence-based indicators. This scientific approach would form a space that is both visually appealing and beneficial to the residents' well-being. Furthermore, the scientifically documented procedure would provide a replicable model for future projects, allowing successful designs to be reproduced in other contexts. Even if the final design has negative consequences after implementation, these drawbacks may be tracked and assessed because all the details were carefully documented and scientifically grounded.